
ICT LITERACY OF LIBRARY PROFESSIONALS WORKING IN LAW COLLEGES

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Abstract:

The present research was undertaken to reveal the status of ICT Literacy of library professionals working in Law colleges affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University Pune. ICT has entered every sector of human life; the library is no exception for it. The challenges have been discovered and discussed in the paper to develop ICT skills among library professionals. Addition to that probable solution is incorporated. A survey method and online questionnaire were used for the collection of the data. The research found that (82.4%) of the respondents are working as librarians, hence, the majority of the respondents are in the main position. It also reveals that due to tight work schedules of 12 (75%) librarians were not able to attend workshops and training programs. Still (82.4%) of the respondents completed their computer education to enhance their skills of ICT. However, research concludes that all librarians require training to enhance their ICT skills.

Keywords: *ICT Literacy, Law Colleges, Library Professionals, ICT Competencies, Digital Library.*

Introduction:

Due to advancement of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) every aspect of human life is the current basis. Impact of e learning visible in the field of education and being affected main alterations in how education is being imparted. (Kondhari, Monika, 2018)

Library and Information Science Profession (LIS) has played an important role in providing the best education and for providing valuable information to their clientele by using (ICT) Information and

Communication Tools. The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) has defined the ICT as computers, satellite and wireless technology and Internet” The usage of technology has been enabled to libraries for preserving and disseminating appropriate information not only to their users but also outsiders as well. Considering the value of ICT, library and information professionals must acquire the adequate knowledge and skills to manage their libraries. This attempt is to reveal the status of ICT literacy and its

challenges of LIS Professionals working in law colleges affiliated to Savitribai Phule

Pune University, Pune

Literature Review:

There have been a number of studies carried out on ICT literacy on library professionals. Thus, careful study of literature was carried before this study.

This article examines the existing information, digital, and computer literacy frameworks and professional competency standards ground algorithmic literacy. It proceeds to identify various elements of algorithmic literacy within existing literature, provide examples of algorithmic literacy initiatives in academic and non-academic settings, and explore the need for an algorithmic literacy framework to ground algorithmic literacy initiatives within the legal information profession.(Garingan and Pickard 2021)

The cross-sectional study and survey were conducted among the library professionals. There was a need to encourage library professionals to participate in workshops, conferences and seminars to stay updated with current trends in modern libraries. The study found that library staff in the Medical College Libraries was not adequate. (Parmar, 2019)

The purpose of study was to explore the essential digital competencies for developing and managing digital libraries. The study identified useful training programs for university librarians to acquire digital competencies. It examined their digital competencies for developing and managing digital libraries in universities of Pakistan. This study also evaluates their digital knowledge in applying security

measures to protect digital contents. (Khan & Bhatti, 2017)

The study investigates the digital preservation practices in institutional repositories (IRs) in Nigeria. The majority of the respondents indicated that they do not have long term funding and lack the necessary technical staff with required skills to handle and manage the IR. The findings will inform information professionals, particularly librarians in developing countries who were planning to create institutional repositories and to provide long-term digital preservation of electronic resources in their institutions.(Kari and Baro 2016)

The study ICT skills among LIS professionals in Assam has determined the proficiency of ICT skills including the awareness of ICT based application, awareness of library automation software, awareness of digital library software, skills for managing electronics resources, skills for managing ICT based library services and the constraints in acquiring ICT skills. (Mahanta, 2016)

The questionnaire-based survey was conducted to analyze ICT literacy among library professionals working in university libraries in Marathwada region. The study gave an overview of the use of ICT based resources and services by library professionals and it helps to know the need of training and orientation in ICT-based resources, services and tools to the library professionals working in university libraries in Marathwada region. The findings of this study show that maximum library

professionals are ICT literate and have significant basic ICT skills to handle the library; but still there was enough scope to develop their innovative ICT skills and implement these skills in the library to provide new ICT-based library services more effectively and efficiently. (Bansode, 2015)

Another study aims to provide a selected bibliography of recent resources on library instruction and information literacy. Study Provides information about each source, discusses the characteristics of current scholarship, and describes sources that contain unique scholarly contributions and quality reproductions. The information may be used by librarians and interested parties as a quick reference to literature on library instruction and information literacy.(Marie Johnson, Sproles, and Detmering 2013)

This study focused on (ICT) literacy among the library professionals of Calicut University. The use of digital library and institutional repository software was very low among the library professionals. Majority of the professionals had confidence in routine ICT and Internet tasks, and need training or orientation in library automation, digital library and institutional repository software. (Haneefa and Shukkoor 2010)

Need and Importance of the Study:

As there are a number of studies carried out to know the status and competencies of ICT is done for library professionals but there is no study for library professionals working in law colleges as the law library professionals are closely associated with online legal information

services. To cater the needs of user's law library professionals are dealing with ICT based services. The judiciary and compliances of law are becoming IT and ICT based, courts are becoming e-courts, legal compliances are becoming e-compliances. Thus the skill for being part of such an IT driven system, has made it mandatory for the Legal Education institution and Law Colleges to impart all these skills through the teaching and learning techniques. Therefore, it is necessary to study the status of ICT Literacy and the challenges of library professionals working in law colleges affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune. This study will encourage librarians, users and policymakers, researchers and practicing legal professionals.

Objectives:

1. To know the status of ICT literacy of LIS Professionals working in Law colleges affiliated to SPPU.
2. To find out the challenges for developing ICT Literacy of LIS Professionals working in Law colleges affiliated to SPPU.
3. To identify and provide the most probable solutions to acquire ICT Skills for LIS Professionals working in Law colleges affiliated to SPPU.

Scope:

The study was undertaken to reveal the status of ICT Literacy of library professionals working in Law colleges affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University Pune, India.

Methodology:

The present study utilized a survey method. The online questionnaire sent to respondents with closed ended questions for the study. There are 27 law college libraries in the study area, among them 16 law college libraries have responded. The analysis and results were presented in the form of graphs and figures.

Data Analysis and Presentation:

Qualifications wise distributions:

Graph No 1 shows that most of the (58.8%) library professionals completed their qualifications with M LIB ISC and (NET) National Eligibility Test and (SET) State Eligibility Test and (17.6%) respondents completed M LIB ISC and Ph.D respectively. Only (5.9%) completed the M.Phil program. So. Majority of the respondents (librarians) completed their post-graduation with NET – SET qualifications.

Graph No. 1: Qualifications wise distributions

Gender-wise distribution:

Graph No.2 shows that (52.9%) respondents are from females and (47.1%) are from male respondents. So, the majority of the respondents working in the law colleges affiliated to SPPU are females.

Graph No.2: Gender-wise distribution

Designation-wise distribution:

Graph No. 3 reveals the professional qualifications of library professionals under study. It was found that (82.4%) of the respondents are working as Librarian and (11.8%) of the respondents working as Library Assistant and (5.9%) of the respondents are working as Assistant Librarian. So, Majority of the respondents are working in Librarian positions.

Graph No. 3: Designation-wise distribution

Level of ICT Literacy:

Graph no. 4 shows that the (70.6%) respondents are at Intermediate level and (29.4%) respondents are at an excellent level in ICT Literacy. Thus, the majority of respondents will consider themselves as Intermediate level.

6. How do you rate your level of ICT Literacy for managing library?
17 responses

Graph No 4: Level of ICT Literacy Computer Education:

Graph No.5 reveals that (82.4%) respondents completed their computer education to develop ICT literacy and (11.8%) responses as may be – it means they don't have surety of their computer ability. But most of the respondents completed their computer education to enhance the skills of ICT.

7. Have you completed any computer education to develop ICT Literacy?
17 responses

Graph No.5: Computer Education Literacy of electronic resources:

Graph No. 6 shows that the literacy of electronic resources. The below graph indicates that the (94.1%) of respondents having their knowledge of legal databases, E Books awareness and literacy of E Journals subsequently. Whereas (70.6%) of the respondents given their literacy with E Newspapers and others literacy includes Magazine's (64.7%), E thesis – (52.9%) and E Publishers – (47.1%)

8. Please indicate the literacy of different electronic resources?
17 responses

Graph No. 6: Literacy of electronic resources

Literacy of Online discussion groups and social media:

Graph No. 7 depicts ICT literacy of online discussion and social media of all respondents' library staff. Out of 16 librarians, 16 (100%) were using social media and 10 (62.5%) librarians had experience of discussion groups and audio/video sharing, while 6 (37.5%) had literacy of blogging, and others 5 (31.3%) respondents had a RSS feeds knowledge, while 3 (18.38%) Listservs and 4(25%) had a wikis knowledge. Thus, all librarians 16 (100%) have knowledge of social media.

9. Literacy of Online Discussion Groups and Social Media ?
16 responses

Graph No. 7: Literacy of Online discussion groups and social media

Literacy of Library Automation Software:

It is evident from the graph no. 8, out of 16 librarians, 9 (52.9%) had literacy of library automation software of KOHA, 6

(35%) librarians had SLIM21 and E Granthalaya respectively. 5 (29.4%) had knowledge of SOUL software whereas 2 (11.8%) had LYBSIS software knowledge, 1 (5.9%) had literacy of Vriddhi, Autolib, Biyani, Smart Schools respectively.

10. Literacy of Library Automation Software ?
17 responses

Graph No. 8: Literacy of Library Automation Software

Literacy of Modules of Library Software's:

Librarians were asked to whether they have a knowledge of different modules available in Library Management Software, Graph No. 9 shows that 14 (82.4%) had a circulation modules whereas 13 (76.5%) librarians had cataloguing and 11 (64.7%) had Administrative and Acquisition module respectively, while 8 (47.1%) librarians had a knowledge of Reference Service, 1 (5.9%) Web OPAC.

11. Literacy about different modules of Library Automation Software ?
17 responses

Graph No. 9: Literacy of Modules of Library Software's

Literacy of Digital Library and Institutional Repository Software:

Graph No. 10 depicts that most of the librarians i.e. 11 (73.3%) had a Dspace software knowledge and 8 (53.3%) had a knowledge of GreenStone Digital Library software.

12. ICT Literacy of Digital Library and Institutional Repository Software ?
15 responses

Graph No. 10: Literacy of Digital Library and Institutional Repository Software

ICT Literacy of Search Engines:

Graph No. 11 reveals that 16 (100%) librarians had Google search engines literacy and 8 (50%) literacy of Yahoo, 3 (18.8%), while 1 (6.3%) MSN and others respectively.

13. ICT Literacy of Search Engines ?
16 responses

Graph No. 11: ICT Literacy of Search Engines

Initiation of ICT based services in library:

Librarians were asked if they have initiated any ICT based services in the library, responses revealed that 11 (64.7%) had initiated ICT based library services, 2 (11.8%) were not started any service pertaining to ICT while 4 (23.5%)

responded as may be. Thus Most of the librarians started the ICT based services in their library.

Graph No. 12: Initiation of ICT based services in library

ICT Based Services:

As the majority of the librarians had initiated ICT based library services, for further investigations, librarians were asked which services they have started in the library. Graph no 13 reveals that 10 (83.3%) started Web OPAC, 7 (58.3%) Current Awareness Service (CAS), 6 (50%) Selective Dissemination of Information (SDI), 4 (33.3%) started indexing services, 2 (16.7%) started Abstracting and Bibliographic Services respectively. Only 1 (8.3%) librarian responded as legal databases. Thus, most of the librarians started (Web OPAC) Online Public Access Catalogue facility in their library.

Graph No. 13: ICT Based Services

Methods of acquiring ICT Literacy:

Librarians were asked to how they are acquiring ICT Skills for enhancing capabilities and ICT literacy. 12 (75%)

librarians responded as they were attending seminars and workshops to gain the ICT Knowledge, 9 (56.3%) getting training at workplace, 8 (50%) trial and error method and self-study method respectively. 7 (43.8%) librarians acquired knowledge from colleagues and friends and information education respectively, while 6 (37.5%) librarians gained ICT Skills from formal education whereas 5 (31.3%) were using web based solutions to acquire ICT knowledge.

Graph No. 14: Methods of acquiring ICT Literacy

Obstacles in acquiring ICT Literacy:

Librarians were asked whether they are facing any problems to acquire new knowledge on (ICT) information and communication technology. Graph No. 15 reveals that 12 (75%) librarians were responded as tight work scheduled, 6 (37.5%) librarians mentioned as lack of awareness and inadequate training respectively, 4 (25%) librarians responded as lack of support from authority and 3 (18.8%) responded as lack of experience with ICT, lack of coordination among library staff and negative attitude of staff

respectively. 1 (6.3%) responded as personal inability.

Graph No. 15: Obstacles in acquiring ICT Literacy

Training needs in ICT Literacy:

Librarians were asked whether they required any training needs to acquire ICT literacy, responses revealed that out of 16 librarians 16 (100%) required training needs. So, all librarians require training to enhance ICT skills.

Graph No. 16: Training needs in ICT Literacy

Areas needs for trainings:

Graph No. 17 reveals that the area of trainings needs for enhancing ICT competencies, 13 (72.2%) responded as ICT tools and equipments, 12 (66.7%) responded as Evaluation of web based and search and free digital services respectively, 10 (55.6%)

mentioned required trainings in electronic legal databases, 9 (50%) Library Automation Software, 8 (44.4%) mentioned as search and free digital reference services, 5 (27.8%) responded as Operating System and Computer and Storage device, 1 (5.6%) responded as day to day new technology are introduced.

Graph No. 17: Areas needs for trainings

Findings and Conclusions:

1. It was found that (82.4%) of the respondents are working as Librarian and (11.8%) of the respondents working as Library Assistant and (5.9%) of the respondents are working as Assistant Librarian. So, Majority of the respondents are working in Librarian positions.
2. The majority of respondents will consider themselves their level of ICT literacy is at Intermediate level.
3. Most (82.4%) of the respondents completed their computer education to enhance the skills of ICT.
4. All librarians 16 (100%) have knowledge about social media and most of the librarians i.e. 11 (73.3%) had a Dspace software knowledge.

5. Almost all librarians had Google search engines literacy and even they have started the ICT based services in their library.
6. Most of the librarians started (Web OPAC) Online Public Access Catalogue facility in their library.
7. Total 12 (75%) librarians responded as they were attending seminars and workshops to gain the ICT Knowledge
8. Due to their tight work schedules of 12 (75%) librarians were not able to attend workshops and training programs.
9. Almost all librarians require training to enhance ICT skills.

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